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The Role of Socio-Economic Status in Vulnerability to Flood Hazard

Literature review

Talking about the literature written about the problem of the role of the socio-economic status in vulnerability to flood hazards, we have to stress, first of all, that the problem discussed is a very important and actual one, because destructions and tragedies associated with natural hazards, still remain very high, especially in countries with low socio-economic status. There are different works written about this question which we will describe in this review.

The problem of floods and hazards caused by them is mostly concerned so-called Third World countries due, firstly, to south climate specifics and, secondly, to the financial impossibility of their government to cope with danger. Of course, we can also see the floods even in Europe: e.g. Germany, Poland, the Netherlands (Schmidt et al, 2006), but these countries usually quickly eliminate the negative consequences after the tragedy, unlike Asian countries (e.g. India, China, Turkey or sub-Sahara African countries) where floods can lead to large numbers of tragedies and deaths. As it is rightly said, disasters are a result of a complex combination of both vulnerability and hazard. Therefore, countries with different socio-economic status react in a different way towards natural flood disasters (Hewitt 1997), because vulnerability is strongly affected by socio-economic status of every given country.

Of course, the easy answer to a problem would be avoiding dangerous places for living, but as Bryant (2005) rightly argues, an important socio-psychological factor is that “people born in an area tend to want to stay there” due to “historic identity with the area which is difficult to give up”. Therefore, the problem of human vulnerability towards flood hazards, response and dealing with them still remains very actual one.

In his work *Natural Hazards* Bryant (2005) describes accurately all the possible phases of interacting of humans with flood hazards, making sub-paragraphs of the following ones: 1) before the event: preparedness, warning and evacuation; 2) dealing with event: response during the event, death, possessions, anti-social behaviour, resettlement 3) additional impacts: emotional problems, stress syndromes. He examines carefully all the subsequent phases of what a person can face while being attracted by the flood.

The warning of disaster is a very important phase, possible to protect people from tragedies. As Bryant remarks (2005, p.273), if people “could recognize the potential for hazards for their environment, and respond to their occurrence before they happened, then there would be minimal loss of life and property”. However, he later observes (2005, p.275) that “those of low socio-economic status, ethnic minorities and women respond least to warnings” due to lack of information or inability to handle mentally or physically.

Patrick S. (2002) in his research “*The future of flood forecasting*” has justly argued that forecasting is an effective management tool for preventing consequences of flood disasters. From socio-economical side, community preparedness for possible flood disaster means spread of forecasting and warning systems. The key for this measure is to prepare people for the possibility of flood because, as we know, well-informed means well-armed. People informed about forthcoming flood may quit their houses and save their belongings and lives. However, nobody would argue that supporting the army of social workers and scientists, responsible for this forecasting, strongly depends upon the financial status of the state, which, in its turn, is the mirror of the socio-economic status of the community.

Quantitative side of forecasting (like satellite imageries and radar systems), effective for floods warning, needs huge financial investments as well: “Large sums of money have been spent on sophisticated flood forecasting systems... in Britain” (Smith 1998, p.280). Ideally, we should have similar attitude towards the disasters in the countries of the Third world. The same concerns the measures undertaken to lessen the losses, like evacuation. As Bryant justly argues, “The decision to evacuate is an economic one. Any evacuation costs

money, no matter who organizes it” (2005, p.275).

Another good socio-economic example of facing the flood hazards lies in reconstruction, post-hazard works and “cleaning up after the disaster” Bryant (2005, p.278) which, in its turn, requires help additional forces from the government side.

Besides warning, another effective strategy of the dealing with floods, according to Smith (1998), can be achieved by land use planning, which would help preventive management and draw attention to the most vulnerable areas. Accurate mapping of the land types and geomorphology (especially floodplain lands) can highlight territories, most vulnerable to floods; “such essentially voluntary controls have been effective in limiting floodplain encroachment in the UK” (Smith 1998, p.282). Using maps and satellite imageries contributes to the effectiveness of the disaster management, such as people relocations and evacuation. In Wisconsin, as cited as an example in Smith text (1998, p.283), the relocation of the whole district at Soldiers Grove, US, was much better decision than post-flooding restoration: “a relocation of the entire business district would yield more benefits than just flood damage reduction for the large cost of the structural scheme”. But for such decisions well-argued opinion and assessment of the specialists is absolutely necessary, what can only be possible in the medium or high socio-economic status societies.

Carey M. (2005) analyzed disastrous outcomes for vulnerable people, comparing the different affects of floods in Peru. Numerous deaths, illnesses, disablements of people are among the most evident results of flood in this country.

Among most evident socio-economic factors influencing the vulnerability, Cutter (2006) mentions paralyzed economic system in the region after the tragedy which concerns even the people who were not directly affected by the flood. Other serious negative factor is loss of property (damaged, destroyed or swept away), which may take several years to recover, especially for poor people who do not have any investments in banks. Replacement of simple livelihood things from household can be easily made in countries where people have credit cards but a very difficult process for those who had poor financial situation. This idea is supported by another author: “class relations and structures of domination are crucial for explaining vulnerability to floods” Blaikie (2004, p.132).

Another problem of vulnerability of the Third World people towards flood hazards that Bogardi J. (2004) described, is the socio-economic structure of countries affected: Third countries are mostly agricultural, and the fields are affected by the floods thus making very difficult to recover after the event and to restore the economy, whereas high developed European countries has much more high-tech oriented economy structure which is not influenced directly: computers, banks, engineering, etc. On the contrary, in the agricultural countries of the Third world “lost” fertile land (destroyed by the erosive capacity of the floods) means almost death for the economy of their countries.

Among other factors of socio-economic vulnerability towards flood hazards, Neumayer and Plumper (2007) mention gender, as women are more likely to be prone to post-flood diseases, usually as a result of their lower social status, therefore, poorer financial situation and nutrition, and as a result, worse health conditions. Concerning age, the same can be said about children due to their more fragile health than that of adult persons.

To the interesting authors investigating this problem we should add Alcántara-Ayala I. (2002) who did a good analysis of relationships between geomorphology, i.e. physical geographic conditions of the area, possible hazards and people’s vulnerability towards them. Besides the detailed description of geomorphology and different kinds of natural hazards (i.g. related to earthquakes), he investigated the problem of human response and vulnerability, or

how people living in dangerous areas encounter problems of hazards.

Ability to take under control and sometimes to correct the forces of nature can reduce strongly vulnerability of people to flood hazards (Lind N et al, 2009). At the same time, controlling these huge nature mechanisms requires good economic investments. There are different mechanisms of how people can reduce their influence, mostly by controlling them: regular scientific observation in form of hydrographs, construction works, such as channelization and dams. Some good examples sets P.Abbott (1996, p.318): “the Mississippi river would have changed its course in the 1930s if the US Army Corps of Engineers had not dredged the channel bottom and built bigger levees” .

Interesting psychological nuance has been marked in Abbott’s work about the urbanization of areas: “the presence of a dam gives a feeling of protection that invites many people to settle in the protected floodplain” (Abbott, 1996, p.314). Thus, constructing dams will not only lessen vulnerability of the area to flood hazard, but, helping to get rid of fear in the minds of people, it can be a good investment into the urbanization and settlement of this territory.

A sorrowful but brilliant example of socio-economic influence to the vulnerability towards floods he gives in bad cooperation and non-agreement in management of Tijuana River, common both for the USA and Mexico. Being able to construct concrete dam on the US side, the Americans saved themselves from the floods which at the same time became a disaster for less prosperous Mexicans. The text is illustrated with a photo showing “flood waters... blasting into the farms and subdivisions in southernmost San Diego” (Abbott, 1996, p.312) exactly in the other side of the state boarder.

Alexander in his fundamental research *Natural Disasters*” (1993, p.524) highlights three possible types of flood hazard effects upon the developing countries: health (including diseases and deaths), agriculture (loos of crops, stocks, seeds) and economy (damage to property, housing and building). Talking about impact of flood hazards upon developing countries he firstly remarks that these countries are most vulnerable towards this disaster geographically: “40% of all cases occur in the Third World”. Together with the fact that these countries are traditionally with low socio-economic situation, it makes a problem of vulnerability is especially sharp in this region: “one in 20 people in India are vulnerable to flooding” (Alexander, 1993, p.524).

There are also indirect consequences of the following upon the life conditions of the poorest strata of society: “widespread destruction of crops, food stocks and food distribution systems... lead to food shortages and malnutrition, especially among infants and poorest, most isolated sectors of the community” (Alexander, 1993, p.527). Particularly, he explains in details the consequences of flood for Bangladesh, as a country affected by flooding most of others, and gives examples of flood disasters impacting upon agriculture, which is the main source of life support for low-income people in this area. Author concludes (Alexander, 1993, p.524) that “the impact on settlement and the economy comprises damage to housing, buildings and infrastructure, loss of household effects, depreciation of property, reduced output loss of business income and rising prices” which creates in the Third World “distinctive and particularly serious outcomes”.

Floods influence hardly the physiographic and hygienic conditions of life in general: negative effect upon water supply, sewage disposal and general sanitation in development countries (Few R. 2007). Concerning human’s health, author mentions different physical aspects of numerous disasters and the human impact and response upon them (from deaths and illnesses to psychological shocks, degeneration of moral and loss of motivation).

Nevertheless, we would finish with optimistic words of Blaikie (2004, p.219):

“Vulnerability can be decreased... even the most vulnerable [people] can recover in such a way that future vulnerability is reduced. Assessing the risk must involve both the social vulnerability information and that concerning the natural hazard, using both sides of the “pressure” model”. These words are perfectly proved by a good illustration of another author (Alexander, 1993, p.525): “high death tolls in storm surge floods in Bangladesh... where there has generally been no warning, no evacuation and near-instantaneous impact. In contrast, recent cyclone impacts in the Caribbean have involved only a handful of deaths, thanks to adequate forewarning and rigorous evacuation”. This citation perfectly illustrates the role of socio-economic status in vulnerability to flood hazard.

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